

THE FIBER-PLACEMENT PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The future emphasis of composite manufacturing in the 1990s will have low-cost manufacturing and process automation as a premium. The fiber-placement technologies in both the thermoset and thermoplastic arenas are well positioned and striving to meet those challenges. The processing differences of the current state-of-the-art fiber-placement processes of thermoplastics and thermosetting systems will be discussed. A comparison of conventional thermoset composite-fabrication limitations associated with filament winding and tape laying will be drawn with the fiber-placement process. An emphasis will be made on the newly developed seven-axis fiber-placement machine by Cincinnati Milacron in a joint evaluation and demonstration program with Thiokol. A description of the FPX machine will cover fiber delivery, machine capacity, axes of motion, software, and processing highlights. Part demonstration of the complex geometries, such as a multisegment cone and a nonaxisymmetric subscale prototype jet engine inlet duct, will be featured.

1. INTRODUCTION

Meeting the challenges of the 1990s requires that composite manufacturing methods become more cost efficient. Aerospace, marine, and industry applications will be considering the inherent benefits (high stiffness and strength-to-weight ratios) composite materials have to offer, but will be discouraged to use composites when manufacturing methods for complex geometries are considered. Since the birth of the composites industry in the late 1940s, engineers have diligently been inventing and improving machinery to make composite manufacturing more cost competitive.

Fiber placement manufacturing is one of the newer developments to meet the challenge. Development of the fiber-placement technology stems from an outgrowth of filament winding, robotics, and automated tape-laying processes. The resulting process is one which has a propensity to reduce composite manufacturing costs.

The fiber-placement process utilizes a material form which is moderately processed by the material suppliers. The fiber-placement *in-situ* process compacts individual prepreg tows into a collimated tape-like band directly on a mandrel or mold surface. The placement of the materials directly onto the mold eliminates a number of processing steps in comparison with hand lay-up methods, thus being more cost efficient.

The automated fiber-placement process broadens the manufacturing limits of conventional composite manufacturing methods in the areas of: in-process material debulking, placement of material

directly onto complex surfaces, automated manufacturing of constant or varied wall thickness, and a complete complement of fiber angles. The fiber-placement process consists of pulling tow material from a spool. The pulling action is created by pinching (or compacting) the material between the mandrel in combination with a machine motion, i.e., rotation or linear movement. Robotics are employed to maintain a compaction roller normal to a mandrel surface as the fibers are placed. The fiber-placement machine has mechanical devices which can be programmed to cut and restart (add) the individual tows as desired.

2. STATE OF THE ART (SOTA)

The fiber-placement process can be divided into two distinct categories: thermoset and thermoplastic (TP) fiber-placement processes. The basic principles of operation are similar for both processes: in-process compaction, robotics to maintain the compactor normal to the mandrel surface, and differential tow payout. The processing differences are obviously due to the material form (thermoset versus thermoplastics). The material form makes the two processes completely different due to the fiber handling and processing requirements. A TP fiber-placement system is inherently complex due to the required high processing temperatures—315° to 427°C (600° to 800°F). When these high processing temperatures are coupled with complex robotic movements, the time element of the equation to in-situ process TP materials becomes very difficult to control with standard hardware.^(1,2) Both the TP materials and the TP fiber-placement process are novel and still in a state of inventiveness to realize low-cost manufacturing capacity.

Present SOTA TP systems are still too slow 9.1 m/minute (30 ft/minute) to be considered for large-scale composite structures.^(3,4) Other companies and academia are pursuing similar methods to implement TP fiber-placement technologies.^(5,6)

The material handling of the two different fiber-placement systems is quite different again due to the nature of the materials. Table 1 summarizes the major differences which affect the mechanical design of the delivery systems.

TABLE 1. Prepreg Tow Comparison

Category	Thermoplastics	Thermosets
Tack Level	None (constant)	Low to high (varies)
Tow Width	48 to 64 mm (0.190 to 0.250 in.) (constant)	24 to 40 mm (0.095 to 0.160 in.) (varies)
Cross Section	Rectangular (constant)	Oval (varies)
Despooling	Zero force	0.45 to 2.2 kg (1 to 5 lb) (varies)
Resin Build-up on Rollers	None (constant)	Low to high (varies)

The TP material packaging and uniform material consistency make the mechanical delivery system from the spool to the fiber-placement head simple in comparison with the thermoset material requirements. The TP's tow prepreg materials will not twist, rope, or gum up a delivery system, which is a problem with thermoset systems. A thermoset delivery system must be periodically cleaned to reduce overall machine downtime.

The major difference in the two processes is in the methods and economies involved in curing or consolidating the materials. The TP fiber-placement has the capacity to *in situ* consolidate the tow

prepreg materials. The thermoset fiber-placement systems must use conventional curing methods which require additional facilities and operations. The thermoset fiber-placement process has the short-term advantage because it can utilize existing proven material systems with a large database. This short-term advantage will be seen in the automation of complex geometric parts which are presently hand laid. The TP processing method in the long term will become a more economical manufacturing approach as processing improves and the materials develop a strong database.

3. THERMOSET PROCESS COMPARISONS

There are other composite manufacturing methods which are closely related to the fiber placement process.⁽⁷⁾ There are subtle differences in filament winding and tape laying which do not put them in the fiber placement category. Tape laying may or may not be included as a true fiber-placement process. The tape-laying process starts with the collimated tape which is inherently limited to geodesic paths. These geodesic paths are limited to only small changes in contours, either concave or convex, to prevent the material from wrinkling. The tape-laying process overlaps fiber-placement in the areas of in-process compaction and the ability to fabricate localized build-ups. Tape layers are programmed line-conventional computer numerical controlled machine tools (i.e., one axis at a time), whereas robotics and programming in the world coordination system are fundamental to fiber-placement machines.

The filament-winding process has even more processing limitations than tape laying. The overlapping technology of filament winding is that it takes individual tow materials and forms them into a collimated band and "guides" the band onto a mandrel. Filament winding does not have in-process compaction, but relies on tension wound hoops for compaction. The final fiber delivery roller moves in a programmed path which is not in contact with the mandrel. The filament-winding process requires a minimum of two machine axes. The winding pattern must be maintained on a geodesic path with minimal fiber slippage. The process is limited to convex bodies of revolution with concave shapes possible with additional manual processing.

The filament-winding process used helical winding patterns to create off axis fiber angles. The helical winding patterns are actually two plies of plus and minus interspersed bands. The intersections of interspersed bands are usually referred to as cross overs and may cause a slight decrease in material strength due to undulations in the fibers. The fiber-placement process is capable of laying down unidirectional off axis-fibers, similar to a tape lay-up.

4. FPX MACHINE

This section will discuss the machine elements and capacities of the FPX fiber-placement machine. The first FPX machine was designed for the thermoset material systems, such as epoxies and bismaleimide; however, the basic machine design is flexible enough to accommodate a thermoplastic tow placement head. The FPX machine is the first production prototype to be built by Cincinnati Milacron for Thiokol under a joint evaluation and demonstration program.

4.1 Fiber Delivery. The FPX machine (Figure 1) is a seven-axis robotic-type fiber-placement machine which is controlled by Milacron's Acramatic 975F computer numerical controller.⁽⁸⁾ This machine is a result of almost 10 years of development.⁽⁹⁾

The machine's sophisticated delivery head and software control system defines the SOTA. The fiber delivery system is comprised of the machine elements which guide the prepreg tow material from the spool to the mandrel. The spools are placed on digitally controlled bi-directional tensioners which are needed to take up slack in the individual tows as the machine goes through its robotic motions.

FIGURE 1. FPX Fiber-Placement Machine

The 24 individual tows travel through various guide rollers to a servo-driven redirect roller on the top of the deliver head, which maintains fiber alignment during the machine's motions. The tows then travel through the heart of the system where the cut/clamp/restart (CCR) mechanisms are located. Additionally, the tow materials are cooled prior to entering the CCR to make the prepregs stiff and boardy so they are easier to handle. The desired tows are either pushed by individual nip rollers or pulled through the machine by the machine motions. The tows are heated to increase their tack just prior to being compressed between the flexible pneumatic compaction roller and the mandrel surface. Table 2 summarizes the fiber delivery systems features.

TABLE 2. Delivery System Summary

Feature	Benefits
<i>In-situ</i> Compaction	Flexible compaction roller, part conformance to 15.2 cm (6 in.) cross-band radius
Bi-directional Tensioners	Digitally controlled, 0 to 6.8 kg (0 to 15 lb) tension capacity +/- 113 g (0.25 lb) tolerance, networked to 975F controller
Servo-driven Redirect Roller	Maintains fiber alignment, reduces tow twisting
Resin Tack Control	Cools tow for machine manipulations, warms to increase material tack, aids in debulking and nesting the fibers
Individual Tow Payout	Capacity for individual fiber speeds, nongeodesic paths (steered fiber paths)
Cut/Clamp/Restart Mechanism	Adjustable band width, add and drop tows, controlled part thickness, 24 tow capacity

4.2 Machine Capacity

Diameter	2.134 m (84 in.) swing
Length	8.687 m (342 in.) maximum
Weight	9,091 Kg (20,000 lb)
Inertia	32,000 in.-lb/sec ²

4.3 Machine Axes. The FPX has seven axes of machine motion. These axes are made up of two linear axis and a carriage tilt axis plus a mandrel rotational axis and three additional rotary axis in the robotic wrist. This machine configuration gives a complete complement of motion to maintain the tool center point (compaction roller) normal to a mandrel surface. These machine axes include the following:

Axes of Motion:

Carriage Axis:	Linear motion of carriage assembly
Cross Slide Axis:	Linear motion of cross slide perpendicular to carriage
Mandrel Axis:	Rotational motion of mandrel parallel to carriage
Tilt Axis:	Rotational motion of the carriage about a point to facilitate vertical motion of the wrist
Robotic Wrist:	Contains three additional axes (Roll 1, Roll 2, Roll 3)

The three axis of the robotic wrist are located on the end of the cross-slide axis. The robotic wrist is not configured in the conventional manner. The three axis of robotic wrist (Roll 1, Roll 2, and Bend) move together to achieve roll, pitch, and yaw for the delivery head.

4.4 Software. The FPX machine is programmed in the world coordinate system through the 975F controller. The 975F controller's 32-bit microprocessors and up to 120 megabytes of optional program storage capacities provide enough processing power to provide high-speed instantaneous input/output interfaces to control the 86 different mechanical and pneumatic devices.

The off-line software is used to generate machine instructions and simulate the instructions in a graphics workstation environment. There are five main modules (Figure 2) in the software package: a translator to import mandrel surface definition, a path generator to provide interactive generation of paths or plies, a post-processor which converts path data into FPX machine control code, a simulation animation generator, and a simulator.

A mandrel surface is defined with a commercial design package such as SDRC's I-Deas or PDA's PATRAN Plus. Depending on the design package, the surfaces are written to either an I-Deas universal file or a PATRAN neutral file. Once the mandrel surface definition is created and written to a supported file, it may be translated for use in the path generation module and/or as a mandrel model for simulation.

Path generation may be performed by generating single paths on geodesic, constant slip factors, fixed angle, planar, or point-to-point paths. No fiber-placement machine motion commands are created during path generation. This helps to move the path generation process into the design loop, thus giving the design engineer more direct control of the as-built composite. As the fiber placement process matures, manufacturability tests will be included in the design loop at the path generation level.

After path generation is complete, the path files are post-processed to create fiber-placement machine motions on and off the mandrel surface to a part program file which is used to process the ply. Collision of the placement head and tooling may be tested using the machine simulation software in conjunction with the Silicon Graphics workstation (Figure 3). The system allows the programmer to

FIGURE 2. Logic Flow of Software

view a simulation of the FPX machine and mandrel going through its robotic motion in real time. This is highly beneficial for first-time part-pattern checks to determine if the collision-avoidance software must be activated. The collision-avoidance software “tweaks” the machine motion transformations so that the machine maintains a normal position in a slightly different plane. For example, the head can be rolled about the compaction roller a few degrees to provide clearance for the structural components of the delivery head. The head can be viewed in an unlimited number of perspectives on the workstation.

FIGURE 3. Fiber-Placement Simulation

4.5 Fiber-Placement Process. Due to the developmental state of the fiber- placement process and the fact that no production parts are being manufactured today, its machine processing capabilities have not been fully explored. The process is capable of steering fibers off of the geodesic due to differential tow pay-out. Figure 4 shows a simple illustration of the steering capabilities. The advantages or limits of this unique processing alternative have not been defined. In steering the fibers on a short radius, 12.7 cm (5 in.), the process may be decreasing the strength of the material due to microbuckling of the fibers.

FIGURE 4. Steered Fibers

However, steered fiber paths have been demonstrated on bodies of revolution to produce a constant fiber angle over a changing surface geometry. Steered fiber paths will make it possible to keep the fibers parallel or in a closer proximity various structural load paths, to increase the part performance.

The ability to add and drop tows from the band adds some interesting manufacturing features. The individual tows can be cut sequentially to produce a saw-tooth-like pattern which forms an angled cut at ply boundaries (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5. Angled Tow Cutting

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Adding and dropping tows can be used to make built-up regions in the lay-up or to decrease material in various regions of a part. A constant thickness part can be created in this manner or one which increases in thickness. Figure 6 shows a schematic of how the tows look after a tow has been dropped from the outermost tows of a band. The software is capable of being programmed to produce bands with any desired amount of overlap on adjacent tows as a tow is dropped. This overlap is created by side-by-side band orientation, not intraband.

FIGURE 6. Dropped Tow Overlap

5. PART DEMONSTRATION

The FPX machine is capable of fabricating a wide variety of complex geometries. The parts which are conducive to fabrication with the FPX machine are in a size range which is at least larger than a volume of 30.5 x 36 x 61 cm (12 x 14 x 24 in.). Other part requirements which are conducive to fiber placement with the FPX machine are nonaxisymmetric, complex lay-up requirements, or are hand-laid because the process could not be automated in the past, and is a body of revolution or can have a shaft installed. Parts which are assembled into a box-like structure may be able to be fiber-placed in one unit for a reduction in part count, and costs.

The parts which have been demonstrated were mainly to test the machine functions, debug the process, and gain an understanding of what fiber placement has to offer the industry. A simple cylinder, cone-shaped part, and a prototype air-inlet duct were fabricated.

The cone-shaped part (Figure 7) was used to demonstrate a number of the processing features previously discussed. The cone-shaped part is comprised of a geometry that has a large cone shape, a small-diameter cylinder section, and another cone facing the opposite direction of the first. The cone's 16-ply lay-up of ICI Fiberite's T300/934 12K tow is shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 7. Fiber-Placed Cone Shape

FIGURE 8. Fiber-Placed Cone Quasi-isotropic Lay-up

Summary of the Cone's Features

- Constant fiber angles (+/- 75, +/- 60, +/- 45, 0, and 90 deg)
- Constant wall thickness
- Zero-degree axial plies
- Localized axial stiffeners
- Localized off-axis build-ups

A generic subscale aircraft jet engine inlet duct was fabricated using the FPX machine as a machine verification part (Figure 9). The geometry has no planes of symmetry. One end has a rectangular cross section (with a relatively small corner radius) which blends to a circular cross section at the other end. In the axial direction of the duct snakes upward and inboard as it transitions from the rectangular to the circular cross sections. Because of this complex geometry parts similar in nature are either fabricated with a number of individual metal parts or hand laid up with composite cloth materials. Both alternatives result in an expensive part with a lower strength or stiffness-to-weight ratio than a comparable fiber-placed part.

Fiber placement of the duct incorporated some unique manufacturing processes which resulted in a low-cost, high-performance part in comparison to the alternative fabrication methods available. The geometry of the duct is a result of its being an integral part of the aircraft. Loading conditions for the duct are analyzed with respect to how the duct is situated relative to the aircraft's orthogonal coordinate system; thus optimal fiber paths for the duct are with respect to aircraft's coordinate system. In manufacturing the duct the position of the aircraft's coordinate system relative to the tool's rotational axis is skewed. The robotic capabilities of the fiber-placement machine make it possible to maintain the aircraft's coordinate system. Furthermore, the fibers can be steered to keep them in the desired orientation.

The assembly of the duct onto an aircraft required built-up regions for attaching fasteners into the composite. The FPX machine was able to automate these built up regions in the desired locations with the appropriate fiber angles with minimal hand lay ups required. These built-up regions were both radial and axial to the part.

6. CONCLUSION

The fiber-placement process is a very versatile composite manufacturing method which was created to reduce composite manufacturing costs through automation. The process in its infancy, and has demonstrated new manufacturing options not previously possible with conventional methods, such as filament winding and tape laying. Material testing will be the next major processing verification step in quantifying the design and manufacturing allowables of the fiber-placement process. Fiber placement may be a vehicle in which composites can finally be designed and manufactured as a composite instead of "black metal". The FPX's sophisticated software used to program a fiber-placed part makes the design, manufacture, and programming processes concurrent. because all those functions overlap in the software. Fiber placement in both the thermosetting and thermoplastic material systems has numerous benefits which need to be matured into a production capacity.

BIOGRAPHY

Mark L. Enders joined Thiokol Corporation in 1985 and is presently a senior process development engineer. His responsibilities include implementation of a seven-axis fiber-placement system. Prior responsibilities include the development of thermoplastic filament-wound pressure vessels and development of an automatic tape-laying/filament-winding machine for cylinder applications, braiding, and internal pressure-molding processes. In 1980, Enders graduated from Clarkson University with a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering and from Oneonta State University of New York with a B.A. in Studio Art. Prior to his employment with Thiokol, he was employed as a research and development engineer for the commercial plastics industry. Enders has published three technical papers.

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